

Nucleic acid (PCR) and antibody (IgG) tests: the course of SARS-CoV-2 infections in the German population unveiled

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Abstract

In Germany, a consortium of authority-accredited laboratories (ALM) covered about 90% of all SARS-CoV-2 PCR tests during the ‘Corona era’ (March 2020 until January 2023), and they likewise conducted serological mass tests for IgG antibodies until May 2021. We analysed these ALM-observed time courses of PCR and IgG tests, their respective test-positive fractions in particular. We found that the week-resolved time course of the IgG-positive fraction can be well reproduced by the cumulative sum of the preceding, likewise week-resolved, PCR-positive fraction values. For this, just one multiplier (0.14) had to be fitted, which means that only 14% of those who were tested PCR-positive actually got infected by SARS-CoV-2. For a second analysis, we took the ratio 1:10 between one positive PCR test and the corresponding number of actually SARS-CoV-2-infected persons, which is documented in the literature as specific for Germany, and estimated the time course of the latter within the German population. At the end of 2021, the courses of IgG-positive and infected fractions align well with the IgG-positive fraction (92%) reported by the Robert-Koch-Institut (RKI). At the beginning of the SARS-CoV-2 mass vaccination campaign on 27/12/2020, a quarter of the German population already carried IgG antibodies from natural infections in their blood. This fact must have been known to the authorities and questions the urgency with which the vaccination campaign was propagated.

Key words: infectious disease; epidemiology; epidemic dynamics; CoViD-19; serology

1. Introduction

Detecting, through amplification, specific nucleic acid sequences of viral genes by carrying out real-time quantitative, reverse transcription polymeric chain reaction (PCR) tests from a mucosal swab of a selected person provides a representation of the presence of viral parts in the mucus outside the mucosal surface of this person’s mucous membrane. Active virus material entering the mucus may be bound, and possibly already neutralised, by IgA antibodies, which are continuously produced in the mucous membrane [1]. If upon *breaching* the mucosal barrier—‘breach’ meaning an invasion of a person’s organism by the active virus material—an increase of IgA concentration can be detected as a response also in the blood, it is common scientific terminology to say that ‘the person had got infected’ [2]. At least in most infection cases, in which symptoms of disease occur, IgG antibodies will also

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be detectable in the blood [3] as another immune response somewhat delayed to the IgA occurrence in the mucous membrane. In fact, as a natural consequence of an infection, the immune system of the infected responds with a multitude of processes, one of which is the production of IgA inside the body, and, delayed, IgG antibodies (plus another three types: IgD, IgE, IgM), which then all circulate in the blood; antibodies are part of the body's *memory* of infections.

Taking data on *severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2* (SARS-CoV-2; family *Coronaviridae*, genus *Betacoronavirus*) infections as a recent virus example, in more severe illness cases, IgG antibodies are detectable about two weeks after the instant of infection, i.e. some time during the second week after onset of symptoms [3]; in milder cases, it takes up to four weeks after infection [4, suppl. fig. 1]. IgG antibodies then remain detectable until a year later at least in more than 90% of the SARS-CoV-2-IgG-positives [5]. Accordingly, in the course of an epidemic virus spreading in a population, the fraction of persons within the population who have IgG antibodies in their blood indicates what percentage of the population were infected in the past. In other words, if a *group* of persons within a population is selected randomly and *tested for IgG antibodies*, the *fraction* of this group *showing IgG antibodies* in their blood, i.e. being *IgG-positive*, *reflects* the sum of all those *infected* in the population until two weeks before, probably even until seven days before [6].

After the emergence of SARS-CoV-2 in late 2019, PCR testing [7] for virus-specific genetic material in mucous nasopharyngeal membranes became a world-wide diagnostic gold standard. It is noteworthy that PCR tests merely scan for *presence of* viral proteins and not an *infection with* active virus material. Still, it can be assumed that there exists a virus-characteristic likelihood that an individual becomes infected, if virus material of some kind is detected in its mucous membrane. Therefore, the population's IgG-positive fraction should be *in proportion to* the sum of all individuals having been tested PCR-positive in the past until two weeks before the IgG testing. However, this only applies if any PCR-positive person has only been tested positive *once* during an analysed time period; in other words, positive *cases* should approximately equal *persons*. Studying the PCR-IgG relation and its quantitative proportion is important, because PCR-test positives were taken as proxy for the number of potentially infected, and used to derive public health policy measures. In this regard, it is important to note that two factors can be identified to increase the number of false positive PCR tests. First, a study [8, p.6] ascertained in 2020 that the screening part of the Charité's PCR test assay tagged *water* controls positive at cycle threshold (CT) values in the range 36-38. Second, based on the Bayesian law of conditional probability, the relative portion of *false* positives naturally rises in times of dropping SARS-CoV-2 prevalence, due to the finite specificity of PCR tests. In addition, it is established that there is no infectiousness in individuals whose PCR tests require cycle CT values of 30 and higher to indicate 'positive' [9, 10], whereas practice was to run tests with CT values up to 40 [11, 12].

In a nutshell, a PCR test takes a *snap shot* of a body's *present exposure* to some virus-specific genetic material at the outer surface, the shield, of the body. Considering common epidemiological wording, the PCR-positive fraction may thus be interpreted as a somehow proportional measurand for the normalised incidence of viral (here, SARS-CoV-2) infections. Contrary to the definition of 'incidence' used in the German Infection Protection Act § 28a(3) "Infektionsschutzgesetz", this fraction does not depend on the actual number of tests conducted, and thus constitutes a more robust measurand for the frequency of infection events. In other words, the incidence normalised to the number of tests, as used here, identifies the 'population size' in the denominator of the incidence definition as the often time-varying number of persons tested within which the tests were conducted, rather than an arbitrarily chosen pool of people with a fixed size, as e.g. the population of a county. A virus-specific

IgG test, then again, informs on a body’s immune response to a hypothesised *past infection* with the specific virus; namely, whether an infection had occurred or not through a virus-specific finite infection *memory* period. Accordingly, the IgG-positive fraction is the portion of a population actually infected by a virus in the past, i.e. the evidence of the collective response of all individuals immune systems’. Mathematically spoken, the population’s IgG-positive fraction at some instant should thus be proportional to the normalised PCR-positive incidences cumulated until then, at least in the first year after the initial occurrence of the virus. This ignores the few percent inaccuracy due to limited IgG test sensitivity, a range from 80...81% [13], 83...86% [6], 91% [14], 97.5% [5] to 100% [15], and sometimes absent, i.e. ‘negative’, sero-conversion [16, 17], with *both* phenomena rendering the actual number of infected *higher* than the observed IgG-positive fraction.

Consequently, in this study, we examine to which extent the PCR-positive normalised incidence, a weekly snap shot, in the German population after emergence of SARS-CoV-2 corresponded to the IgG-positive normalised fraction, the immune systems’ memories, based on data provided by the same authority-accredited labs. Eventually, we use this cross-checked information contained in the time courses of lab-reported PCR and IgG tests, and two parameter values from the literature, to estimate the time course of the fraction of actually SARS-CoV-2-infected persons within the entire German population.

2. Materials, Methods, and Results

We have checked the week-resolved relation between the cumulative sum of the fraction of positive PCR test counts and the corresponding fraction of positive IgG test counts in the specific time period from mid March 2020 until the end of 2021 in Germany. The data were taken from a webpage [18] at which a medical lab consortium (*Akkreditierte Labore in der Medizin e.V.*, Berlin, Germany; short: ALM) of German test labs reported their results of weekly counts of PCR and IgG tests, respectively, both absolute numbers and positive portions. The consortium continuously ran about 90% of all PCR tests in Germany [19]. The time course of these counts are plotted in Fig. 1(A), resolved by calendar weeks (CWs; numerical symbol: *cw*); here, *cwX(Y)* denotes CW X in year Y, e.g. *cw10(2020)*, the tenth CW in 2020. The corresponding weekly ratios of positive test counts and all those carried out, i.e. the fractions of positive PCR and IgG tests, respectively, are plotted as percentages in Fig. 1(B): the small squares connected by a dashed line represent the ALM-observed data of the PCR-positive fraction, and the big circles symbolise the ALM-observed data of the IgG-positive fraction. Also plotted is the course of the scaled cumulative sum of past values of the PCR-positive fraction (thick line with plus signs in Fig. 1(B)), which best reproduces (technically expressed in short: fits) the ALM-observed IgG-positive fraction by a simple model estimate. To be more precise, for each given CW, at which the observed IgG fraction is sought to be estimated by the scaled cumulative sum, the past PCR-positive fractions are summed until two CWs before. This sum is then multiplied by a factor P_{PCR} of proportionality, and an offset $O_{IgG,0}$ is added to the sum, which reflects the unknown value of the IgG-positive fraction two weeks after the time of start of summation. Expressed as a formula, this simple model estimate of the IgG-positive fraction in CW number *cw* from the preceding and delayed PCR-positive fractions summed is

$$F_{IgG,cw} = O_{IgG,0} + P_{PCR} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{cw-2} F_{PCR,i} \quad . \quad (1)$$

Here, $F_{PCR,i} = \frac{N_{PCRpos,i}}{N_{PCR,i}}$ is the observed PCR-positive fraction in each CW *i* until *cw* – 2, assuming IgG antibodies are first detectable only two weeks after infection, and $F_{IgG,cw}$ is

the estimated IgG-positive fraction in CW cw , with $N_{PCR,i}$, and $N_{PCRpos,i}$ being the weekly observed PCR counts of the numbers of PCR tests and their positive ones, respectively. The IgG-positive fraction $F_{IgG,i} = \frac{N_{IgGpos,i}}{N_{IgG,i}}$ observed in each CW i is given by the observed weekly IgG counts $N_{IgG,i}$, and $N_{IgGpos,i}$. By determining the parameter values $O_{IgG,0}$ and P_{PCR} , using the MATLAB (Version R2024b, The MathWorks, Natick, MA, USA) function ‘lsqnonlin’, the estimated sample sequence $F_{IgG,cw}$ was least-squares-fitted to the correspondingly observed sequence $F_{IgG,i}$. The ALM reported their first PCR data point in $cw11(2020)$. To capture the full width of the ‘first SARS-CoV-2 wave’, we linearly back-extrapolated the PCR-positive fraction $F_{PCR,i}$ for three weeks ($cw8(2020)$: 0.005, $cw9(2020)$: 0.02, $cw10(2020)$: 0.035; see ‘PCR-pos., 3 cws back’ in Fig. 1(B)), assuming that there were very low to vanishing levels of the PCR-positive fraction until $cw7(2020)$. Consequently, $i = 0$ in Eqn. (1) corresponds to $cw8(2020)$.

Our primary and major parameter finding of least-squares fitting the model $F_{IgG,cw}$ (Eqn. (1)) to the ALM-observed sample sequence $F_{IgG,i}$ is the parameter value $P_{PCR} = \frac{1}{7.15} \approx 0.14$ (confidence interval, CI: 0.135...0.146); i.e. we estimate the portion of IgG-positive cases within all PCR-positive cases having been about 14%; the estimated value of the IgG-positive fraction at $cw10(2020)$, $O_{IgG,0}$, was -0.001 , i.e. $-0.1\% \approx 0$ (CI: $-1.1\% \dots 0.9\%$). With $P_{PCR} \approx 0.14$, or 14%, the model estimate $F_{IgG,cw}$ by Eqn. (1) (thick line with plus signs in Fig. 1(B): ‘ALM: (cum. PCR-pos. frac.)/7.15 + (0)’) well fits the ALM-observed data points $F_{IgG,i}$ of the IgG-positive fraction (circles in Fig. 1(B): ‘ALM: IgG-positive fraction’): the mean residual of the fit per sample, i.e. the square root of the sum of the squared residuals over all 61 samples normalised to the number of samples, was 0.28%. The estimate $F_{IgG,cw}$ further allows to extrapolate beyond the ALM’s IgG observations terminating in $cw21(2020)$, until the model-estimated fraction $F_{IgG,cw}$ reaches 1 at the beginning of 2022. $P_{PCR} \approx 0.14$, or 14%, tells us in particular that only one in close to every seventh ALM-detected PCR-positive person statistically proved to be IgG-positive. Note that the latter sentence is an *inference* based on a specific *assumption*, which we make here due to our lack of knowledge of the criteria that determined the (pre-)selection of persons for being IgG-tested: We *assume* here, for the time being, that the latter were among those having been PCR-tested.

Keeping this *assumption* in mind, only about 14% of all PCR-positive persons were actually infected by SARS-CoV-2, according to the ALM data. As the pre-selection criteria in *both* groups, the PCR-tested—e.g. antigen tests or clinical examinations preceding—, and the IgG-tested—e.g. a family doctor’s patient asking for its immune status—, are intransparent to the public, and maybe even widely unknown to or undocumented by the ALM themselves, we discuss further below (Sec. 3.1) the above *inference*, which pivots around the value of the factor P_{PCR} . We do this by hypothesising an additional scaling factor to P_{PCR} , which represents the net ratio of the two pre-selection likelihoods of whether a PCR- or an IgG-tested person had actually been SARS-CoV-2-infected at the time of the test.

Second, what is more, we estimated the time course of the fraction $F_{infec,cw}$ of SARS-CoV-2-infected persons *within the entire German population* ($N_{pop} = 83.5 \cdot 10^6$ inhabitants in Germany). For this, we transferred the statement “For any positive PCR test, there are actually about 10 SARS-CoV-2 infections.”, which recapitulates empirical findings in Germany [20, p. 59: $U_{infec} \approx 10$] and Switzerland [21, SEROCO-V-POP: $U_{infec} \approx 11$], into another simple phenomenological formula:

$$F_{infec,cw} = O_{infec,0} + \frac{U_{infec}}{R_{ALM}} \cdot \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{cw} N_{PCRpos,i}}{N_{pop}} \quad . \quad (2)$$

Here, the estimate $F_{infec,cw}$ of the entire German population’s SARS-CoV-2-infected fraction

is assumed to first of all depend on the $F_{infec,cw}$ value $O_{infec,0}$ of the infected fraction at $cw10(2020)$ ($O_{infec,0} = \frac{O_{IgG,0}}{2} = 0.01 = 1\%$ as a simple guess), i.e. before the first week $cw11(2020)$ ($i = 0$) of known PCR data, second, the empirically known approximate number U_{infec} of infections per positive PCR test (value chosen: 10), and, third, the likewise known parameter R_{ALM} (value chosen: 0.9), which accounts for the ALM having continuously run about 90% of all PCR tests in Germany [19]. The chosen value $U_{infec} = 10$ is fully consistent with the ratio $\frac{\text{infection fatality rate (IFR)}}{\text{case fatality rate (CFR)}} \approx 10$ that can be determined for Germany from $CFR \approx 0.025$ [22, r_{PF} in tables 3, 4], and $IFR \approx 0.0021 \dots 0.0025$ [23, ‘Germany’ in table 4]. The phenomenological model estimate $F_{infec,cw}$ of the time course of the German population’s SARS-CoV-2-infected fraction according to Eqn. (2) is plotted as a thin brown line with small crosses in Fig. 1(B) (‘infected population from cum. PCR positives’). From November 2020 on, $F_{infec,cw}$ generally lies in a range 2...6% below the ALM-observed IgG-positive fraction, along with its fitted estimate $F_{IgG,cw}$ (Eqn. (1)), only to eventually exceed from $cw46(2021)$ on the fit $F_{IgG,cw}$ to the ALM-observed IgG-positive fraction, extrapolated towards the end of 2021. At the turn of 2021 into 2022, extrapolated $F_{IgG,cw}$ shows a value of about 92%, which perfectly coincides with the value given by the Robert-Koch-Institut (RKI) [24, 25], 92%, while the entire population’s estimated SARS-CoV-2-infected fraction has reached its theoretical maximum of $F_{infec,cw} = 1$ (i.e. 100%) exactly then. The steep $F_{infec,cw}$ slope towards the end of 2021 owes, numerically, to the peak of the absolute count of PCR-positive tests around $cw47(2021)$ (Fig. 1(A)). The infected fraction apparently reaching 100% therefore indicates that lately in autumn 2021 the number of PCR tests must have deviated from the number of persons tested. The corresponding multiple testing per person has been suggested as a phenomenon in [22, sec. 3.3; tables 5, 6]. Accordingly, the $F_{infec,cw}$ slope steepening and its crossing of $F_{IgG,cw}$ cannot be deemed a reliable finding. In any case, taking $F_{IgG,cw} = 0.92$ in $cw52(2021)$ as a guide, together with the course of the $F_{infec,cw}$ estimate until $cw43(2021)$ (then about 65%; Fig. 1(B)), the fraction of Germans having been SARS-CoV-2-infected at least once must have reached at least 85% at the end of 2021, which is indeed a conservative guess given 92% reported by the RKI.

Eventually and notably, another parameter value has been found here. During the vaccination campaign of the first half of 2021, the fraction of people showing IgG antibodies in their blood increased by 1.1% per week, which is the approximate slope of a least-squares-fitting straight line through the last 12 samples of $F_{IgG,i}$, i.e. circles until $cw21(2021)$ in Fig. 1(B). The slope (likewise from least-squares fitting) of the ALM-observed IgG fraction curve $F_{IgG,i}$ before the start of the vaccination campaign (end of 2020, circles in Fig. 1(B) from $cw45(2020)$ through $cw52(2020)$), which was definitely caused by solely natural infections, was steeper, namely, 1.8% per week.

3. Discussion

3.1. Sensitivity of inferences on the population’s course of infections: considering pre-selection probabilities of tested persons

We start our discussion with reflecting on an obvious potential objection to directly estimating, by a linear relation of lab-observed PCR- and IgG-positive test fractions in weekly selected sub-populations in Germany, the average percentage of persons with a PCR-positive test that has actually been infected by SARS-CoV-2. As an alternative to assuming that the IgG-positives are simply a sub-group of all those having been PCR-tested, one might hypothesise that those tested by ALM for IgG antibodies were a nearly random selection of patients in Germany who saw a doctor due to any health problem conceivable. This alternative assumption would foster the inference that the ALM-observed IgG-positive fraction may have

German SARS-CoV-2 test counts vs. calender week (cw)

(A)

German SARS-CoV-2 test fractions vs. calender week (cw)

(B)

Figure 1: (A) Absolute numbers—taken from [18]; still available only in part at [19]; IgG data only discontinuously and until CW number cw53(2020); fully available as **supplementary material** [26]—of both PCR (mucous; *small hollow squares*) and IgG antibody (serological; *asterisks*) tests for SARS-CoV-2 carried out weekly by ALM in Germany 2020-2022, and their positive portions (*small solid squares* and *circles*, respectively); for better visibility, IgG counts are multiplied by ten.

(B) Fractions (ALM-observed, given in percent) of both positive PCR ($F_{PCR,cw} \cdot 100\%$, *small solid squares*, *dashed line*) and IgG ($F_{IgG,cw} \cdot 100\%$, *big circles*) tests, i.e. the respective ratios of positive portions and absolute numbers of tests carried out. Also shown (details: see main text): the scaled cumulative sum $\sum_{i=0}^{cw-2} F_{PCR,i}$ of past values (until two CWs ago) of PCR-positive fractions providing a fit to the time course of the ALM-determined IgG-positive fraction ($F_{IgG,cw} \cdot 100\%$ fitted according to Eqn (1), *thick line with plus signs*), three back-extrapolated data points (at cw8(2020)-cw10(2020)) to estimate the initial course (*thick hollow squares*) of the PCR-positive fraction $F_{PCR,cw}$, as well as the estimate of the fraction of SARS-CoV-2-infected (i.e. carrying IgG antibodies: $F_{infec,cw} \cdot 100\%$ according to Eqn. (2), *thin line with small crosses*) in the entire German population, calculated from the cumulative sum $\sum_{i=0}^{cw} N_{PCRpos,cw}$ of all PCR-positive persons since the start of ALM observations (in cw11(2020)). Additionally, two RKI-reported [24, 25, 27, 28] IgG-positive fraction values of the entire population are plotted (*thick plus signs*).

been close to representative of the entire population. As a consequence, the IgG-positive fraction might then have indeed been potentially *higher* within the somehow pre-selected (by the authorities’ test strategies) PCR-positive ALM clientele than in the ALM-observed IgG-positive clientele; this case would eventually yield $P_{PCR} > 0.14$. Accordingly, P_{PCR} would increase in direct proportion with the ratio of the probabilities of being infected when screened and therewith positively pre-selected for a PCR test—e.g. by a point-of-care or rapid antigen test, by clinical criteria of illness, or having been contact traced a person tested positive—and when randomly selected for an IgG test. To the best of our knowledge, there is no literature reporting such a ratio of probabilities, e.g. between PCR-positive fractions in a positively pre-selected versus a random group from the same population. Given indeed $P_{PCR} > 0.14$ as a consequence of positive pre-selection, values of the PCR-positive fraction in the entire population would have been generally *lower* than what was weekly reported by the RKI, that is, pre-selection would have generally exaggerated the perception of the infectious SARS-CoV-2 dynamics. Conversely, implying within the PCR-positives an IgG-positive fraction generally *lower* than observed by the ALM (correspondingly hypothesising a lower IgG-positive fraction within the general population) would be accompanied by $P_{PCR} < 0.14$, that is, the percentage of PCR-positives being actually SARS-CoV-2-infected would have to be inferred to be even lower than 14%.

In any case, we again refer to our validity check above, in the second last paragraph of Sec. 2. Namely, even two PCR-positive-fraction-based estimations of the IgG-positive fraction yield remarkably good matches to the corresponding, RKI-observed 92% value reported [24, 25] for the entire German population at the end of 2021: this is, first of all, the extrapolation of the ALM-observed IgG-positive fraction by direct use of parameter P_{PCR} applied to the PCR-positive fraction (Eqn. (1)); this is, second, the estimation of the time course of the SARS-CoV-2-infected by means of a literature-extracted parameter U_{infec} (Eqn. (2)). What is more, the value $U_{infec} = 10$ assigned here is consistent with the ratio of infection (IFR) and case (CFR) fatality rates, likewise known from literature. Eventually, if one assumes as another alternative that *both* signals, the weekly PCR- and IgG-positive fractions, are approximatively random (i.e. representative) samples, then Fig. 1(B)) certainly well reflects the course of SARS-CoV-2 infections in the German population anyway. Furthermore, this remains even true if the PCR-positive fraction observed by ALM was an exaggeration within the entire population by pre-selection, which would eventually imply most essentially that the percentage of PCR-positives, who had actually been SARS-CoV-2-infected, were indeed somehow higher than 14%.

3.2. Conditions of testing, PCR and IgG thresholds, and PCR test specificity

In our view, the result of comparing the P_{PCR} -scaled cumulative sum of observed PCR-positive fractions (Eqn. (1)) with the observed IgG-positive fraction is astounding: Given the utter simplicity of the summation model representing both the physiological details, such as virus presence in membranes or serological antibody responses, and the technological details, such as testing procedures and parameters, behind both test signals, the match of the fit gained by summing and scaling the time course of the past PCR-positive fraction signal (Eqn. (1)) to the directly observed time course of the IgG-positive fraction signal might be considered almost perfect (Fig. 1(B)). The pattern, in spring and summer 2020, of first under-then over-estimation of the ALM-observed IgG-positive course by simply a P_{PCR} -scaled cumulative sum of PCR-positive fractions may be explained by the government changing their strategy in early May to increasingly PCR testing persons without symptomatic cause (so-called ‘mass testing’), and, in summer 2020, by antibody levels partly dropping below test detection thresholds.

Of course, an infection can *definitely not* be ascertained in the individual case from a PCR-positive test, as the collective factor $P_{PCR} = \frac{1}{7.15} = 0.14$ (CI: 0.135...0.146) of proportionality is clearly smaller than 1. Moreover, the factor P_{PCR} is a product in itself of multiple impacting proportionality factors, for example, a practically irreproducible and time-dependent combination of pre-selection criteria of persons tested, non-standardised and time-varying CT values chosen by labs for PCR testing, as well as methods and detection thresholds chosen in IgG testing, such as chemical concentrations or optical densities. All these impacting factors are conflated in the two standard performance parameters of testing, namely, a test’s ‘sensitivity’ and its ‘specificity’; for a nice summary, see [29]. To sum it up, the factor P_{PCR} reflects the net probability of a person to get systematically infected if virus material can be PCR-detected in its mucous membrane; and this probability is about 0.14 (14%, CI: 13.5...14.6%).

The performance parameter relevant to our findings is the overall specificity of PCR mass testing in Germany in 2020 and 2021. Irrespective of the sensitivity of PCR tests (so let us even assume it were 100%), by knowing that the mean weekly PCR-positive fraction (normalised incidence) in Germany from cw11(2020) until cw21(2021), i.e. the period until termination of IgG testing by ALM, had been approximately 7%, and having found $P_{PCR} = \frac{1}{7.15}$ through our fitting, which together disclose a mean pre-test fraction (probability) of about 1% actually SARS-CoV-2-infected persons per week, a specificity of 94% explains that 6% of the actually 99% non-infected in mass testing have been tagged as ‘false positives’ by PCR mass testing, which in turn corresponds perfectly to direct checks of the specificity of PCR tests (see [30, p.362]). A specificity of 94% hence explains that only $\frac{1}{7.15}$ of the PCR-tagged ‘positives’ have actually been SARS-CoV-2-infected, as proven by the ALM’s IgG testing, namely, 1% SARS-CoV-2-infected (‘true positive’) persons in altogether about 7% PCR-tagged ‘positives’. In summary, our finding of $P_{PCR} = \frac{1}{7.15}$ is fully consistent both with the observed low mean PCR-positive fraction and with a Germany-wide PCR tests’ specificity value of 94%.

3.3. PCR test specificity and deaths caused by SARS-CoV-2

A recent analysis of PCR-conditional mortality in Germany until mid 2023 yielded the estimate that no more than about 59,500 persons, out of about 115,500 tagged by the RKI, can be claimed to have potentially died due to SARS-CoV-2 in the full two year period 2020-2021 [22, sec.4.2], i.e. roughly half of the number asserted by the RKI. Both this RKI number and the reasoning for its halving was based on accepting that a positive PCR test indicates ‘being infected by SARS-CoV-2’, with this equating being inherent to the German legislation (the “Infektionsschutzgesetz”). As a consequence of our finding here, the claim is to be further reduced, namely, to only about 14% of 115,500 deaths, i.e. roughly 16,200, being causally attributable to SARS-CoV-2 infections through the two years 2020 and 2021. Accordingly, the question arises what other factors caused the undoubtedly manifest excess mortality in the flu seasons 2020/21 and 2021/22 [22, tab.2] and could explain the difference between estimated 59,500 excess deaths among the PCR positives, for 2020 and 2021 together, and estimated 16,200 deaths among the actually SARS-CoV-2-infected? This question depends on how many of the remaining 86% of PCR-positive persons had not been infected by any virus at all, how many potentially only mildly by SARS-CoV-2, with leaving no detectable IgG traces in their blood, and how many perhaps by other types of viruses, given the degree of non-specificity of PCR tests (Sec.3.2). Non-specificity can be well explained by regularly applying PCR test CT values up to 40 [11, 12], while it seems established (e.g. by the German Paul-Ehrlich-Institut, PEI [9]) that (i) specific information, whether no, mild, or severe symptoms of illness arise, gets lost above CT values of about

27 [11, p. 2, left col.], (ii) infectiousness practically vanishes for CT values increasing from 25 through 30, with the viral load in the mucosal barrier decreasing from $10^6 \frac{\text{copies}}{\text{ml}}$ at a CT value of about 25 [9, 10, 12], and (iii) the probability of the body getting infected, with the blood being invaded and usually symptoms of illness arising, generally decreases with viral load.

3.4. IgG fractions: comparison of lab observations, estimated infections of the population, and two RKI-reported data points

Our estimated fraction of about 24% (Fig. 1(B)) of SARS-CoV-2-infected inhabitants at the start of the German SARS-CoV-2 vaccination campaign on 27/12/2020 is remarkable, because the German authority for health surveillance, the RKI, suggested that maximally 2.8% [27], and ostensibly not even more than 2% [28]) of all Germans had been IgG-positive “until November 2020”, leaving open which cut-off date for this percentage was used exactly. At the time the RKI reported, let us assume mid November (i.e. cw46(2020)), the ALM-observed IgG-positive fraction was 15%, which is perfectly confirmed by its estimate, the P_{PCR} -scaled cumulative sum of PCR-positive fractions (Eqn. (1)); furthermore, our estimated population-wide fraction of cumulatively SARS-CoV-2-infected IgG carriers (Eqn. (2)) was 11%. At that time, the discrepancy between, on the one hand, both the ALM-observed and the estimated IgG-positive fractions, and, on the other hand, the RKI-reported IgG-positive fraction is striking (Fig. 1(B)), in particular, as the ALM data were available to—and even commissioned by—the RKI. The low values of 2.0 . . . 2.8% may be explained by the IgG measuring method employed in the RKI-SOEP study—subjects themselves took ‘dried blood spots’ [27]—being generally too insensitive.

Regarding the discrepancy between the ALM-observed IgG fraction and our generally lower estimate of the population’s SARS-CoV-2-infected fraction (Eqn. (2)), we could neither find information on the IgG testing method(s) employed by ALM, nor on the pre-selection of the ALM clientele tested for IgG antibodies, except all tests being requested by physicians [19], i.e. evidently on occasions of patients seeing doctors for whatever reasons. In any case, the ALM data basis is vast, relying on carrying out between 10,000 and 100,000 IgG tests every week (Fig. 1(A)), German-wide. The reason why the ALM suddenly stopped IgG test reporting in cw21(2021), just when the IgG-positive fraction had reached 50%, is unknown to the authors. It is most remarkable in this context that the RKI reported about 92% [24, 25] for the IgG-positive fraction of the entire German population at the end of 2021, which almost perfectly aligns with *both* our extrapolation of ALM-based IgG-positive fractions from cw21(2021) onwards according to the ALM-fitting Eqn. (1) *and* our simple phenomenological model estimation of the entire German population’s SARS-CoV-2-infected fraction according to Eqn. (2).

4. End section statements

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4.2. Author contributions

MG saved the ALM data from being dumped, analysed them, prepared the graphics, and drafted the introduction, the methods & results, and part of the discussion. RR supported in the analysis, and drafted discussion parts. HW drafted discussion parts. MG, RR, and HW revised and polished the full manuscript iteratively.

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4.4. Competing interests

The authors do not have conflicts of interest of any kind.

4.5. Supplementary material

Supporting information (two data files) is found in the online version of the article at the publisher's website (**supplementary material** [26]).

4.6. Data, code and materials

The complete input data for this study comprise exactly two ASCII-coded (text) files named "PCR_ALM.txt" (weekly counts of PCR tests and their positive portion) and "IgG_ALM.txt" (weekly counts of IgG tests and their positive portion), which have been made available along with manuscript submission (see also 'Supplementary material' section 4.5).

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